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Research Article

**EVALUATION THE ROLE OF SKELETAL MYOBLASTS IN
THE MANAGEMENT OF ISCHEMIC HEART DISEASE**

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Abstract

Background: Cardiac cells regeneration and stem cell therapy have shown a lot of progression in the recent years. Understanding the new technological advances in cell therapy will ultimately allow us to achieve a goal of cell-based cardiac repair.

Objective: in our paper we aim to assess the recent literatures published in this field and provide a simple yet a comprehensive review.

Methods: PubMed database was used for articles selection, and the following keys used in the mesh {skeletal myoblasts, Cardiomyopathies, Ischemic Heart Disease, and Myocardial Infarction}. A total of 47 articles were enrolled according to our inclusion and exclusion criteria.

Conclusion: SKM treatment of IHD have been progressed since its beginning, a lot of obstacles have been solved, but still significant work need to be done to overcome the remaining ones. The recent results are very encouraging, and promising to emphasize more in this filed.

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INTRODUCTION:

In the US, an estimated 15.4 million people have coronary heart disease, of whom 7.6 million are affected by myocardial infarction and 2.1 million by congestive heart failure.[1] Actually this dilemma is not restricted to US alone, but it is a global issue where cardiovascular disease is the leading cause of death worldwide accounting for nearly 17 million deaths per annum according to the World Health Organization.[2]

In ischemic cardiomyopathies, the cardiac cells are injured irreversibly in results to reduced blood supply to the heart tissue, which induces ischemic damage, and ultimately leading to the death of cardiomyocytes, and disruption of cardiac function resulting in what is called heart failure. Despite pharmacologic and surgical approaches, heart failure remains one of the significant diseases lacking the complete cure. So far, the only definitive treatment for heart failure is heart transplantation, which can't be depended on as the first line treatment due to the limited availability of donor hearts and complications from immunosuppressive therapies.[3] Therefore, this has pushed the researchers looking for another options of therapy. In the last two decades, the classical concept of the heart as an organ with extremely limited regenerative capacity has been changed. Different ideas have been developed to induce regeneration of the dead cardiomyocytes by introducing stem cells into the affected area.[4-5] Many types of progenitor cells having the capability to differentiate into heart cells (such as : smooth muscle cells, embryonic stem cells, mesenchymal bone marrow stromal cells, hematopoietic stem cells, and skeletal myoblasts) were tested in vitro, then introduced by different sophisticated methods to determine their possible beneficial effects in vivo.[6] Each one of these stem cells has its own characteristics, which favor some on other. As the skeletal myoblasts proved their capability in multiple experiments to replace the

dead cardiac myocytes with maximum benefits and limited complications, they attracted the researchers to proceed in different detailed trials including the use of various animal models and introduction techniques, multiple transfections overexpressing various factors (modified SkMs), and finally landing up into the human clinical trials.[7]

In this article a critical review including some of SkMs journey in the treatment of ischemic heart disease including their beneficial effects, limitations encountered and their possible solutions, and what is the future prospective of their uses.

METHODOLOGY:**Sample**

We performed comprehensive search using biomedical databases; Medline, and Pubmed, for studies concerned with cardiac cells regeneration and stem cell therapy published between 2013- 2018 in in English language. Keywords used in our search through the databases were as {Myoblasts, Ischemic Heart Disease, Stem Cells, Cardiac Cells Regeneration and Cardiomyopathy}. More relevant articles were recruited from references lists scanning of each included study. A total of 47 article were enrolled into our study.

Analysis

No software was used, the data were extracted based on specific form that contain (Title of the study, name of the author, Objective, Summary, Results, and Outcomes). Double revision of each author outcomes was applied to ensure the validity and minimize the errors.

RESULTS:

A total of 47 articles were enrolled in our study according to our inclusion criteria.

Table 1: List of Included Studies

No.	Articles
1	Matthias Siepe, M.D., Scaffold-Based Transplantation of Akt1-Overexpressing Skeletal Myoblasts: Functional Regeneration Is Associated with Angiogenesis and Reduced
2	Yasuhiro Shudo, MD, Addition of Mesenchymal Stem Cells Enhances the Therapeutic Effects of Skeletal Myoblast Cell-Sheet Transplantation in a Rat Ischemic Cardiomyopathy Model. <i>Tissue Eng Part A.</i> , 2014 Feb; 20(3-4): 728-39.
3	Abdel Shafy, MD, Association of electrostimulation with cell transplantation in ischemic heart disease. <i>J Thorac Cardiovasc Surg.</i> , 2009 Oct; 138(4): 994-1001.
4	Kai Zhu, Transplantation of novel vascular endothelial growth factor gene delivery system-manipulated skeletal myoblasts promote myocardial repair. <i>Int J Cardiol.</i> , 2013 Oct 3; 168(3): 2622-31.
5	Mikhail Konoplyannikov, Activation of Diverse Signaling Pathways by Ex-Vivo Delivery of Multiple Cytokines for Myocardial Repair. <i>Stem Cells Dev</i> , 2013 Jan 15; 22(2): 204-15.
6	Thomas J. Povsic, A double-blind, randomized, controlled, multicenter study to assess the safety and cardiovascular effects of skeletal myoblast implantation by catheter delivery in patients with chronic heart failure after myocardial infarction. <i>Am Heart J.</i> , 2011 Oct; 162(4): 654-662.e1.
7	Jesu ´s Herreros, Autologous intramyocardial injection of cultured skeletal muscle-derived stem cells in patients with non-acute myocardial infarction. <i>Eur Heart J.</i> , 2003 Nov; 24(22): 2012-20
8	Tomasz Siminiak, MD, Autologous skeletal myoblast transplantation for the treatment of postinfarction myocardial injury: Phase I clinical study with 12 months of follow-up. <i>Am Heart J.</i> 2004 Sep; 148(3): 531-7.
9	Philippe Menasché, MD, Autologous Skeletal Myoblast Transplantation for Severe Postinfarction Left Ventricular Dysfunction. <i>J Am Coll Cardiol</i> , 2003 Apr 2; 41(7): 1078-83.
10	Francis D. Pagani, MD, Autologous skeletal myoblasts transplanted to ischemia-damaged myocardium in humans. Histological analysis of cell survival and differentiation. <i>J Am Coll Cardiol</i> , 2003 Mar 5; 41(5): 879-88.
11	TOMOYUKIFUJITA, Clinical Impact of Combined Transplantation of Autologous Skeletal Myoblasts and Bone Marrow Mononuclear Cells in Patients with Severely Deteriorated Ischemic Cardiomyopathy. T Fujita et al. <i>Surg Today</i> , 2011 Jul 20; 41(8):1029-1036.
12	Henricus J. Duckers MD, Final results of a phase IIa, randomised, open-label trial to evaluate the percutaneous intramyocardial transplantation of autologous skeletal myoblasts in congestive heart failure patients: the SEISMIC trial. <i>EuroIntervention</i> , 2011 Feb; 6(7): 805-12.
13	Jens Brickwede, Long-term follow-up after autologous skeletal myoblast transplantation in ischaemic heart disease. <i>Interact Cardiovasc Thorac Surg</i> , 2014 Jan; 18(1): 61-6.
14	Paul Steendijk, Intramyocardial injection of skeletal myoblasts: long-term follow-up with pressure-volume loops. <i>Nat Clin Pract Cardiovasc Med</i> , 2006 Mar; 3 Suppl 1:S94-100.
15	Nabil Dib, MD, One-Year Follow-Up of Feasibility and Safety of the First U.S., Randomized, Controlled Study Using 3-Dimensional Guided Catheter-Based Delivery of Autologous Skeletal Myoblasts for Ischemic Cardiomyopathy (CAuSMIC Study). <i>JACC Cardiovasc Interv</i> , 2009 Jan; 2(1): 9-16.
16	Yoshiki Sawa, MD, Safety and Efficacy of Autologous Skeletal Myoblast Sheets (TCD-51073) for the Treatment of Severe Chronic Heart Failure Due to Ischemic Heart Disease. <i>Circ J.</i> , 2015; 79(5): 991-9.
17	Tomasz Siminiak, Percutaneous trans-coronary-venous transplantation of autologous skeletal myoblasts in the treatment of post-infarction myocardial contractility impairment: the POZNAN trial. <i>Eur Heart J.</i> , 2005 Jun; 26(12): 1188-95.
18	Philippe Menasché, MD, The Myoblast Autologous Grafting in Ischemic Cardiomyopathy (MAGIC) Trial First Randomized Placebo-Controlled Study of Myoblast Transplantation. <i>Circulation</i> , 2008 Mar 4; 117(9): 1189-200.

19	Agnieszka Janeczek, Genetically modified human myoblasts with eNOS may improve regenerative ability of myogenic stem cells to infarcted heart, <i>Kardiol Pol</i> , 2013; 71(10): 1048-58.
20	Robert von Wattenwyl, Scaffold-Based Transplantation of Vascular Endothelial Growth Factor–Overexpressing Stem Cells Leads to Neovascularization in Ischemic Myocardium but Did Not Show a Functional Regenerative Effect, <i>ASAIO J.</i> , 2012 May-Jun; 58(3): 268-74.
21	Britta Blumenthal, Polyurethane Scaffolds Seeded With Genetically Engineered Skeletal Myoblasts: A Promising Tool to Regenerate Myocardial Function, <i>Artif Organs</i> , 2010 Feb; 34(2): E46-54.
22	Britta Blumenthal, Functional regeneration of ischemic myocardium by transplanted cells overexpressing stromal cell-derived factor-1 (SDF-1): intramyocardial injection versus scaffold-based application, <i>Eur J Cardiothorac Surg</i> , 10, 2011; 40(4): e135- e141.
23	Khawaja Husnain Haider, MicroRNA-21 is a key determinant in IL-11/Stat3 anti-apoptotic signalling pathway in preconditioning of SkMs, <i>Cardiovascular Research</i> , 2010; 88: 168–178.
24	Maitane Perez-Illzarbe, Characterization of the paracrine effects of human SkMs transplanted in infarcted myocardium, <i>European Journal of Heart Failure</i> , 10(2008): 1065–1072.
25	Marie-Noëlle Giraud, Long-Term Evaluation of Myoblast Seeded Patches Implanted on Infarcted Rat Hearts, <i>Artif Organs</i> , 2010 Jun; 34(6): E184-92.
26	Matthias Gmeiner, Improvement of cardiac function in the failing rat heart after transfer of SkMs engineered to overexpress placental growth factor, <i>J Thorac Cardiovasc Surg</i> , 2011 May; 141(5): 1238-45.
27	Annika Poppe, Hepatocyte Growth Factor-Transfected SkMs to Limit the Development of Postinfarction Heart Failure, <i>Artif Organs</i> , 2012 Mar; 36(3): 238-46.
28	T.J. Kolanowski, In vitro and in vivo characteristics of connexin 43-modified human SkMs as candidates for prospective stem cell therapy for the failing heart, <i>Int J Cardiol</i> , 2014 Apr 15; 173(1): 55-64.
29	Yasuhiro Shudo, Myocardial Layer-Specific Effect of Myoblast Cell-Sheet Implantation Evaluated by Tissue Strain Imaging, <i>Circ J.</i> , 2013; 77(4): 1063-72.
30	Juan Jose´ Gavira, Repeated implantation of skeletal myoblast in a swine model of chronic myocardial infarction, <i>Eur Heart J.</i> , 2010 Apr; 31(8): 1013-21.
31	Javier Moreno, Skeletal myoblast implants induce minor propagation delays, but do not promote arrhythmias in the normal swine heart, <i>Europace</i> , 2010 Nov; 12(11): 1637-44.
32	Eric Larose, Percutaneous Versus Surgical Delivery of Autologous Myoblasts After Chronic MI: An In Vivo Cardiovascular Magnetic Resonance Study, <i>Catheter Cardiovasc Interv</i> , 2010 Jan 1; 75(1): 120-7.
33	Shigeru Miyagawa, Impaired Myocardium Regeneration with Skeletal Cell Sheets—A Preclinical Trial for Tissue-Engineered Regeneration Therapy, <i>Transplantation</i> , 2010 Aug 27; 90(4): 364-72.
34	Zhuang Wei, Autologous myoblasts transplantation improves heart function after MI, <i>J. of central south university</i> , 2011 Apr; 36(4): 286-93.
35	Ieva Antanavi_c_i_ut_e, Exogenous connexin43-expressing autologous SkMs ameliorate mechanical function and electrical activity of the rabbit heart after experimental infarction, <i>Int. J. Exp. Path.</i> , 2015; 96: 42–53.
36	Changfa Guo, MD, Myoblast Transplantation for Cardiac Repair: From Automyoblast to Allomyoblast Transplantation. <i>Ann Thorac Surg</i> , 2008 Dec; 86(6): 1841-8.
37	TOMMI PAˆ TILA, Improved diastolic function after myoblast transplantation in a model of ischemia-infarction. <i>Scand Cardiovasc J.</i> , 2009 Apr; 43(2): 100-9.
38	Steven R. Coppen, PhD, A Factor Underlying Late-Phase Arrhythmogenicity After Cell Therapy to the Heart Global Downregulation of Connexin43 in the Host Myocardium After Skeletal Myoblast Transplantation. <i>Circulation</i> , 2008 Sep 30; 118(14 Suppl): S138-44.
39	Patrick Farahmand, MD, Skeletal Myoblasts Preserve Remote Matrix Architecture and Global Function When Implanted Early or Late After Coronary Ligation Into Infarcted or Remote Myocardium. <i>Circulation</i> , 2008 Sep 30; 118(14 Suppl): S130-S137.

40	Koen E.A. van der Bogt, MD, Comparison of Different Adult Stem Cell Types for Treatment of Myocardial Ischemia Circulation, 2008 Sep 30; 118(140): S121–S129.
41	Gilbert Dubois, Self-Assembling Peptide Nanofibers and Skeletal Myoblast Transplantation in Infarcted Myocardium. J Biomed Mater Res B Appl Biomater, 2008 Oct; 87(1): 222-8.
42	Husnain K. Haider, Skeletal Muscle Derived Stem Cells for Myocardial Repair. Recent Pat Cardiovasc Drug Discov, 2007 Nov; 2(3): 205-13.
43	Lei Ye, MD, Transplantation of Nanoparticle Transfected Skeletal Myoblasts Overexpressing Vascular Endothelial Growth Factor-165 for Cardiac Repair. Circulation, 2007 Sep 11; 116(11 Suppl): I113-20.
44	Chung-Dann Kan, MD, Recipient Age Determines the Cardiac Functional Improvement Achieved by Skeletal Myoblast Transplantation. J Am Coll Cardiol, 2007 Sep 11; 50(11): 1086-92.
45	Muhammad Idris Niagara, Pharmacologically Preconditioned Skeletal Myoblasts Are Resistant to Oxidative Stress and Promote Angiomyogenesis via Release of Paracrine Factors in the Infarcted Heart. Circ Res., 2007 Mar 2; 100(4): 545-55.
46	Lei Ye a, Angiopoietin-1 for myocardial angiogenesis: A comparison between delivery strategies. Eur J Heart Fail, 2007 May; 9(5): 458-65.
47	Shunsuke Saito, Myoblast Sheet Can Prevent the Impairment of Cardiac Diastolic Function and Late Remodeling After Left Ventricular Restoration in Ischemic Cardiomyopathy. Transplantation, 2012 Jun 15; 93(11): 1108-15

DISCUSSION:

Autologous skeletal myoblasts (SkMs) are the well-studied type of cells which have been extensively characterized in preclinical experimental animal models as well as in the clinical studies. They have many characteristics that support their superiority over other cell types [7] (fig 2). SkMs implanted into infarcted hearts have shown functional restoration in both systolic and diastolic (increased LVEF, segmental contractility, and compliance of the infarcted myocardium), and structural improvement such as delayed LV remodeling, neovascularization, and increased systolic thickening of the scared area beside their safety and feasibility in vitro, in vivo and in human beings as well.[8-10]

As mentioned above SkMs gained the focus from many of research groups having an interest in this field due to their incredible, valuable and beneficial results achieved until now.[8-10] From this stand, many experimental studies of SkMs have been conducted and still lots of studies are under process. Multiple review papers similar to ours have been published and an overall similar results were obtained encouraging more effort, and time to be spent in such a field. Following are some of the strengths and limitations of our project:

Strength

The reviewers were supervised by an experienced person who has multiple publications in this field,

providing them with the most sensitive and crucial points to be addressed. A double revision of the results of each articles included in this paper was carried out, minimizing the possibilities of mistakes and increasing the reliability of the results. This review includes around 47 articles (34 animals studies, 13 human studies) addressing various points of view in each article, which provide an excellent information in the clinical perspective. Finally, we included recent and modern articles (animal studies: last 10 y, human studies: last 5 y), so the people who will read this review will know the most recent progresses and the obstacles still encountered.

Limitations

Firstly, we restricted ourselves to one search engine (PubMed), to collect relevant information. Although this is a global, versatile engine, and is extensively used by researchers as it contains a huge number of articles. However, it doesn't include all of the conducted studies especially the clinical studies in this specific field; increasing the chance of missing an important studies and information relating to our review project. Secondly, this review as mentioned previously, consists of 13 clinical studies, and as the main purpose of the majority of researches is the prioritized concern about safety and efficacy of SkMs. This number of human studies is considered low to support strongly the use of SkMs as a treatment of ischemic cardiomyopathies. Finally, restriction of the reviewed clinical studies to the last 5 years is considered a limitation in the sense that we failed to compare the data emanating from earlier studies.

Challenges:

SkMs are similar to any type of stem cells in term of their advantages and disadvantages. These disadvantages should not be an obstacle in their progress to patient use, instead they should lead the scientists to make efforts to overcome their limitations and maximize their beneficial effects. Transplanted SkMs show an electromechanical isolation from the host myocardium which disturbs the synchronous contractility, and functional integrity of the myocardium, thus inducing an arrhythmia which is considered a major problem in SkMs transplantation.[11] Medical therapy or automatic cardiac defibrillator implantation treat and lower the risk of arrhythmias. Genetic modification of SkMs with connexin 43 overexpression improves functional integration and synchronous contractility through increased amplitude of gap junction conductance with the host myocytes.[12-13] Massive attrition rate, especially in the acute phase affecting negatively the overall results of these experiments.[14] As the early loss of SkMs was attributed to oxidative stress, poor availability of nutrients, lack of adherence with the host tissue and the inflammatory/immune responses, many strategies have been suggested to encounter these issues including ischemic preconditioning of the cells by exposure to multiple cycles of hypoxia and re-oxygenation which found to improve the survival rate of the implanted cells.[15-16]

Future Prospective

Despite the promising results achieved using this type of cells, still there are some issues which need to be resolved for an optimal prognosis. The dose of the cells, route of delivery, and survival duration play an important role on the final results. Optimization of culture conditions preserve the proliferation and differentiation characteristics. Repeated injections have shown better results (reduction in the size of the infarcted area and higher LVEF) as compared to a single dose injection.[17-18] Intramyocardial injection as a route of cells delivery is widely used, although it provides the preciseness of directing the cells into the infarcted area by direct visualization and shows good results, it is an invasive procedure and considered to be proarrhythmogenic. Recently, biological cell-sheet was seeded with SkMs and applied on the infarcted area as a delivery route and found to have an equal positive outcomes, but less traumatic compared to intramyocardial injection. This method allows the adherent cells - seeded sheet on the affected epicardium, by avoiding the needle trauma which lead to less fibrosis and less arrhythmia beside the positive effects.[19-20] Many clinical

studies reported the presence of ventricular arrhythmia in patients receiving SkMs, however and interestingly enough, all reported cases were treated pharmacologically.[21] Genetic modified SkMs overexpressing different cytokines and growth factors found to achieve better results when compared to wild type cells, and enhance the paracrine effect along with the direct effect of stem cells.[22-36] Paracrine mechanisms need to undergo an extensive experiments since it can lead to optimal results. Finally, as in this field the two dominating cells are SkMs and bone marrow stem cells have promising results, therefore, it was suggested that their combination with each other might offer a better results.[37]

In conclusion, as the stem cell therapy is still in infancy, the obstacles encountered should not hinder the researchers to exert an extensive efforts to overcome them, having in mind as an encouragement points all the positive results fulfilled in the clinical experiments until now and that if this therapy achieved its optimal results would reduce the major burden of such a disease. SkMs remain as other types of stem cells which is impossible to be without having disadvantages, but their advantages as previously mentioned overcome their disadvantages leading them to be the most well-studied donor cell type.

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